

CORPUS LINGUISTICS OF PARALLEL LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *The article defines what corpus parallel texts is and how they can enhance learning and effectively scaffold reading proficiency development. In case you want to learn English, parallel Uzbek corpus helps you to learn faster, easier and deeper. In our research, we try to compose and compare both languages by consisting texts. As much, you read parallel texts more you obtain in language learning.*

Key words: *corpus, parallel texts, Uzbek, English, method, monolingual, translation, original text.*

Аннотация. *В статье определяется, что такое корпус параллельных текстов и как они могут улучшить обучение и эффективно способствовать развитию навыков чтения. Если вы хотите выучить английский язык, параллельный узбекский корпус поможет вам учиться быстрее, легче и глубже. В нашем исследовании мы пытаемся составить и сравнить оба языка, составляя тексты. Чем больше вы читаете параллельные тексты, тем больше вы получаете при изучении языка.*

Ключевые слова: *корпус, параллельные тексты, узбекский, английский, метод, одноязычный, перевод, оригинальный текст.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada korpus parallel matnlar nima ekanligini va ular qanday qilib o'rganishni kuchaytirishi va o'qish malakasini rivojlantirishni samarali tarzda rivojlantirishi mumkinligini belgilaydi. Agar ingliz tilini o'rganmoqchi bo'lsak, parallel o'zbek korpusi bizga tezroq, oson va chuqurroq o'rganishga yordam beradi. Maqolamizda biz ikkala tilni matnlarni birlashtirib solishtirishga harakat qilamiz. Qanchalik ko'p parallel matnlardan foydalansak, til o'rganishda ko'proq qulayliklarga erishamiz.*

Kalit so'zlar: *korpus, parallel matnlar, o'zbek, ingliz, metod, bir tilli, tarjima, original matn.*

There is much interest to research corpus linguistics in Uzbekistan last 15 years. First we should understand what is corpus linguistics? Corpus linguistics is the study of a language as that language is expressed in its text corpus (plural corpora), its body of “real world” text. Corpus linguistics proposes that a reliable analysis of a language is more feasible with corpora collected in the field the natural context (“realia”) of that language with minimal experimental interference. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Corpus_linguistics)

Let's determine what is a corpus? A text corpus is a very large collection of text (often many billion words) produced by real users of the language and used to analyze how words, phrases and language in general are used. It is used in all spheres of science like linguists, lexicographers, social scientists, humanities, experts in natural language processing and in many other fields. A corpus is also be used for generating various language databases used in software development such as predictive keyboards, spell check, grammar correction, text/speech understanding systems, text-to-speech modules, machine translation systems and many others which is very useful in our research. In scientific world, large collections of parallel texts are called parallel corpora that is text corpora. Alignments of parallel corpora at sentence level are

prerequisite for many areas of linguistic research. During translation English texts into Uzbek, sentences can be split, merged, deleted, inserted or reordered by the translator. Analysis from Corpora can be used to explore the relationships between Uzbek language and English languages, which have undergone a similar analysis. In case if, Uzbek corpora appears we may use it in our work deriving from small authentic texts. In developed countries that work is automated already and helps students to learn faster. First, we give explanation how does it work.

A parallel text is a text placed alongside its translation or translations.[1][2] Parallel text alignment is the identification of the corresponding sentences in both halves of the parallel text. A famous example is the Rosetta Stone, whose discovery allowed the Ancient Egyptian language to begin being deciphered. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Parallel_text)

Materials and methods. Types of text corpora

It is not possible to easily classify a corpus into a certain category. Instead, corpora can have features or properties, which can be used to group them. The same corpus can have one or more of these features. Language. Monolingual corpus. A monolingual corpus is the most frequent type of corpus. It contains texts in one language only. The corpus is usually tagged for parts of speech and is used by a wide range of users for various tasks from highly practical ones, e.g. checking the correct usage of a word or looking up the most natural word combinations, to scientific use, e.g. identifying frequent patterns or new trends in language. Sketch Engine contains hundreds of monolingual corpora in dozens of languages.

A parallel corpus consists of the same text translated into one or more languages. The texts are aligned (matching segments, usual sentences, are linked). The corpus allows searches in one or both languages to look up or compare translations.

(<https://www.sketchengine.eu/guide/parallel-concordance-searching-translations/#toggle-id-1>)

I have begun working on some parallel Uzbek-English reading texts with exercises for students. I have in mind the new compulsory primary languages policy beginning in September, along with ways of getting students to read longer chunks of language in a painless way.

Here are some examples how to know to each other in Uzbek and English languages.

At first parallel text look little bit strange. On the left hand side, you have your target language response. It might be conversation with person A and B. For beginning students, we have line-by-line basis whatever topic we are learning this is going to be a perfect high-level response in either Uzbek, Russian, Spanish depending on what you have been learning. On the right hand side, you have translation into natural English. This is a word-by-word translation. In the beginning, we should understand how English is different to Uzbek. To complete this technique is like this.

:	Hello. How are you?	A:	Salom. Qandaysiz?
:	I am well thanks and you?	B:	Men yaxshiman raxmat, sizchi?
:	Yes, am very well thanks	A:	Men juda yaxshiman rahmat
	How do you call yourself?		Ismingiz nima?

:	I call myself Chase		Mening ismim Cheyz
	and my best friend calls herself Jenifer		Va mening eng yaxshi do‘stimni ismi Jenifer
:	When is your birthday?	B:	Sening tug‘ilgan kuning qachon?
:	My birthday is eighteenth of June	A:	Mening tug‘ilgan kunim o‘n sakkizinchi 18 iyun
	I was born in two thousand and three I am eighteen years old		Ikki ming uchinchi yilda tug‘ilganman, o‘n sakkiz yoshdaman
	The birthday of my friend is second of april		Do‘stimning tug‘ilgan kuni ikkinchi aprel
	Nice to meet you	B:	Siz bilan tanishganimdan xursandman
	Where do you study?		Qayerda o‘qiysiz?
	I study in AKFA University dental school	A:	Men AKFA Universiteti stomatologiya fakultetida o‘qiyman.
:	Do you study English there?	B:	Siz u yerda inglizcha o‘qiysizmi?
:	Yes we study in English all subjects	A:	Ha biz hamma fanlarni Ingliz tilida o‘qiyamiz.
:	I speak little English	B:	Men bir oz ingliz tilida gapiraman.
	If I study it well I would also like to study at AKFA University too		Uni yaxshi o‘rgansam men ham AKFA universitetida o‘qishni xoxlayman
:	You have six months to learn English well	A:	Sizda Inglizchani yaxshi o‘rganish uchun olti oy vaqtingiz bor
	I will help you.		Men sizga yordam beraman

All in all, To compare two languages we cover and read line-by-line. We say it out loud because we want to make sure that students pronunciation is accurate as we go through. Hello. How are you? Salom. Qandaysiz? That is direct translation that is fine though because it is the same as Uzbek. I am well thanks and you? Men yaxshiman rahmat, sizchi ? Here in English we may say well and say good. I am well/good. We might say either way. We need to be aware of that as we move down see it is logical. However, in next sentences things might be clunky in the Uzbek. Ismingiz nima? In English should sound as what is your name? Not how do you call yourself? Then we cover left side and right side to compare how we are doing well this exercise. We repeat it several times to learn parallel texts. This kind of technique helps with medical texts as well.

Benefit 1 – They encourage ‘noticing’

Another common occurrence of this process is when our students process our feedback on error and notice the gap between our version and their erroneous output.

Benefit 2 – They can effectively scaffold reading with less confident readers The use of parallel texts as scaffolds for reading is recommended at the early stages of instruction; the translation support will be gradually phased out as the students become more confident.

Benefit 3 – Students learn vocabulary in context. In order to sensitize the learners to the target words in the text, quizzes and other vocabulary activities can be carried out prior to reading the text, which focus the students on those words. This, in my experience, can significantly enhance retention of target lexis.

Benefit 4 – They facilitate access to more challenging texts even in Medicine

Benefit 5 – Differentiation. The best examples of non-electronic parallel texts for lower levels of proficiency I have located on the web so far are found at <http://www.frenchteacher.net>. We think targeting higher levels of proficiency, too. Great interactive online parallel texts can also be found at <http://www.textivate.com>.

REFERENCES

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Corpus_linguistics
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Parallel_text
3. <https://www.sketchengine.eu/guide/parallel-concordance-searching-translations/#toggle-id-1>
4. <https://www.google.com/search?q=PARALLEL+TEXTS+EXAMPLES>
5. https://cysouw.de/home/articles_files/cysouwINTROPARALLEL.pdf
6. <https://gianfrancoconti.com/2015/06/07/870/>
7. Tashpulatova, D., & Siddiqova, I. (2021, April). A CRITIQUE OF THE VIEW OF ANTONYMY AS A RELATION BETWEEN WORD FORMS. In *Конференции*.
8. Тошпулатова, Д. Х. (2019). ПОНЯТИЕ И ВИДЫ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ КОНЦЕПЦИЙ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ. АНАЛИЗ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ КОНЦЕПЦИЙ. *Вопросы педагогики*, (7-2), 118-121.
9. ТАШПУЛАТОВА, Д. PRAGMATIC APHORISMS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH FEATURE AND THE PRINCIPLES OF THEIR TRANSMISSION IN THE CORPUS. *СООТНОШЕНИЕ ПАРАЛИНГВИСТИКИ И РЕЧЕВОГО ЭТИКЕТА В РАЗНЫХ ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРАХ*.
10. qizi Turaboyeva, S. Z., & qizi Tashpulatova, D. X. (2022). O‘ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDAGI AXLOQIY QADRIYATLAR MAZMUNINI IFODALOVCHI BIRLIKLARNING LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Academic research in modern science*, 1(1), 143-147.
11. Ташпулатова, Д. Х. К., & Умурзакова, Б. Э. (2023). ПЕРВНЯЯ СИСТЕМА. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 4(TMA Conference), 303-309.
12. Tashpulatova, D. K. K., & Jiyenbayeva, B. (2023). THE IMPACT OF LEARNING A LANGUAGE ON THE BRAIN FUNCTION. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 4(TMA Conference), 310-314.
13. NAVOI, A., & BABUR, Z. M. (2022). RESEARCH AND EDUCATION.